

After the addition of the peptizing agent, the mixture was shaken mechanically for 1 hr and then centrifuged for about 15 min at 1400 r.p.m. The supernatant layer after centrifugation was collected and 25.0 ml of this aliquot portion was subjected to nitrogen estimation by the modified method of Peach and Tracey⁶.

The results of the peptized nitrogen estimated in term of percentage of the total nitrogen.

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Effect of Viscosity and Inorganic Nucleophiles on the Decomposition of 2-Methylthio-4,5-diphenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazolium iodide

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EARLIER we have presented¹ in detail the mechanism of hydrolysis of 2-methylthio-4,5-diphenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazolium iodide (I) which is an useful intermediate for the preparation of mesoionic s-triazole systems². Despite numerous experimental data in favour of a neutral tetrahedral intermediate (II) at the rate controlling stage, there was no direct evidence against possible intervention by any hydrated complex, such as III, which could possibly arise via an encounter³ with the solvating species (water).

Moreover, some recent observation on cation-anion interaction^{4,5} also prompted us to examine more closely the effect of various inorganic nucleophiles on rate constants in order to identify the possible cause(s) of observed negative salt effect on I. It is in this context that additional experimental data are presented here in support of our previously proposed mechanism of hydrolysis of I.

Experimental

Materials: The substrate (I), m.p. 185-86°, and the inorganic salts (AR grade) were dried under vacuum and stored in a desiccator prior to their use. Methanol was purified as before⁶ and glycerol (AR) was used as such from fresh bottle. Stock solutions (2M) of the following salts in conductivity water were used for adjusting the ionic strength of the reaction medium: NaSCN, NaNO₃, Na₂SO₄, Na₂S₂O₃, KF, KCl, KBr, KI and KCN.

In glycerol-water system weighed quantities of glycerol and water were added to known weights of a stock solution of the substrate (I) in glycerol in order to control the glycerol content (% w/w) of the medium. But in the case of methanol-water system (50% v/v), aliquots of the stock solution (*ca* 1 × 10⁻⁴M) were diluted with requisite volumes of methanol, water and the required salt solution in order to maintain the final ionic strength around unity ($\mu = 1.0$).

Kinetic measurements: In all cases kinetic runs were followed by spectrophotometric technique under neutral condition at 40 ± 0.2° by measuring the fall in absorbance at appropriate λ_{max} (Tables 1 & 2) determined previously through separate experiments. Other experimental details were the same as before^{1,6} and the necessary data are collected in Tables 1 & 2.

Results and Discussion

(a) *The effect of viscosity on rates:* Encounter limited rate constants³ are normally in the range of 10⁹ sec⁻¹ whereas our observed rate constants in 50% methanol or glycerol are in the range of 10⁻⁴sec⁻¹. Nevertheless, it is quite possible to observe³ a small overall rate constant with an encounter limited rate determining step. In this context, rate constants were calculated from kinetic runs in a series of glycerol-water mixtures which form an ideal⁷ solvent for our purpose.

Inspection of data in Table 1 now clearly shows a slow and monotonic rise in rate constant with increasing viscosity or glycerol content of the medium

